

**DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL MARKETS IN THE MIDDLE EAST AND
NORTH AFRICA (MENA): HISTORICAL OVERVIEW, CURRENT STATUS, AND
FUTURE OUTLOOK**

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Abstract

The financial markets of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region exhibit a fundamental duality, with significant progress in infrastructure alongside ongoing challenges related to efficient capital allocation and financial stability. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the historical, current, and future development trends within these markets, categorizing the region into four main groups: Gulf Cooperation Council countries, North Africa and the Levant and Iraq, and fragile states. The findings suggest that growth in Gulf countries is primarily driven by strategic government interventions rather than enhancements in market efficiency. Conversely, North African markets experience slower development due to weak governance and the absence of a well-established bond market. In the Levant, Iraq, and fragile states, functional financial markets are largely underdeveloped or absent, with informal financing mechanisms—such as remittances and commodity-based transactions—playing a predominant role. The study emphasizes that substantial financial transformation depends not only on technological advancement or superficial market listings but also on institutional reforms, legislative harmonization, and the strengthening of investor confidence. Accordingly, it is recommended that governments transition from acting primarily as financiers to assuming the roles of regulators and custodians of the financial system to promote sustainable growth.

Keywords: Financial Markets, Financial Development, Structural Transformation, Corporate Governance, FinTech, Middle East and North Africa Region

**ORTA DOĞU VE KUZEY AFRİKA (MENA) BÖLGESİNDE FİNANSAL
PİYASALARIN GELİŞİMİ: TARİHÇE, MEVCUT DURUM VE GELECEK
PERSPEKTİFLERİ**

Öz

Orta Doğu ve Kuzey Afrika (MENA) bölgesinin finansal piyasaları, altyapıdaki resmi gelişmelere rağmen, sermaye tahsisi ve finansal istikrar açısından yeterli fonksiyonel verimlilik göstermemektedir. Bu çalışma, bölgeyi dört ana gruba ayırarak, söz konusu piyasaların geçmiş, güncel ve gelecekteki gelişimini detaylı bir şekilde analiz etmektedir: Körfez İş Birliği Konseyi ülkeleri, Kuzey Afrika ve Şam ile Irak bölgesi ve zayıf devletler. Bulgular, Körfez ülkelerindeki ilerlemenin piyasa verimliliğinden çok, stratejik hükümet müdahalelerine dayandığını ortaya koymaktadır; Kuzey Afrika piyasaları ise zayıf yönetim ve tahvil piyasalarının eksikliği nedeniyle gelişim açısından geride kalmaktadır. Şam ve Irak bölgesi ile zayıf devletlerde ise fonksiyonel finansal

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piyasa bulunmamaktadır; bunun yerine nakit transferleri ve mallara dayalı resmi olmayan finansman sistemleri hakimdir. Çalışma, gerçek anlamda finansal dönüşümün, teknoloji veya sembolik listelemelerden çok, kurumsal reformlar, mevzuat uyumu ve yatırımcıların güçlendirilmesine bağlı olduğunu vurgulamaktadır. Bu nedenle, devletlerin finansal altyapının sürdürülebilirliğini sağlamak amacıyla, finansör konumundan mevzuatın gözetmenliğine geçiş yapmasının daha uygun olacağı kanaatindeyiz.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Finansal Piyasalar, Finansal Gelişme, Yapısal Dönüşüm, Kurumsal Yönetim, FinTech, Orta Doğu ve Kuzey Afrika Bölgesi*

1. Introduction

Financial markets form a fundamental component of modern economies, providing essential information about investment opportunities and promoting the efficient allocation of capital. They also function as mechanisms for institutional oversight and governance after financing has been provided. Additionally, financial markets facilitate the trading of financial instruments, support risk diversification and management, mobilize savings, and direct those savings toward productive investments. Furthermore, they enable the exchange of goods and services, contributing to overall economic efficiency (Levine, 2005: 5).

Financial markets within the MENA region face several structural challenges stemming from a weak regulatory and operational environment that constrains commercial activity and access to finance. Although there have been some superficial improvements in certain financial systems, access to credit remains significantly limited compared to other regions, which hampers the growth and innovation potential of businesses—particularly small and medium-sized enterprises. Additionally, cross-border trade processes entail considerable burdens, with exporting typically incurring costs of approximately USD 442 and requiring around 53 hours to comply with regulatory requirements—these figures are three times higher in cost and four times longer than those in high-income OECD countries. Further obstacles include elevated fees within the insurance and transportation sectors, as well as regulatory policies that restrict transport services, collectively reducing supply chain efficiency and delaying the development of essential logistics infrastructure for trade finance. Addressing these institutional challenges is crucial for the development of deep, inclusive, and sustainable financial markets in the region (World Bank, 2021: 58, 60).

Financial markets across the MENA region exhibit considerable diversity in their institutional frameworks, resilience to economic shocks, and integration with the global economy. The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries—such as the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, and Saudi Arabia—possess substantial fiscal reserves that have facilitated the implementation of effective fiscal and monetary policies during periods of crisis, including wage support and credit easing measures. Additionally, these nations have successfully raised billions of dollars through international bond markets to bolster liquidity. In contrast, countries such as Libya, Syria, and Yemen experience institutional challenges characterized by unreliable data, limited analytical capacity, and a

significant decline in exports due to ongoing armed conflicts. These conflicts, along with trade barriers and political isolation, impede trade integration and heighten economic vulnerabilities, particularly in neighboring states that rely heavily on remittances or host large refugee populations, such as Jordan and Lebanon. This variation underscores a notable intra-regional disparity: some economies are better equipped to withstand shocks owing to sovereign wealth and robust institutions, while others remain vulnerable to ongoing fragility, which tends to intensify with each crisis (World Bank, 2021: 4–5, 9, 28, 30, 42–43, 50).

This study classifies the MENA region into four geographically and economically coherent subregions: Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries (Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Kuwait, Bahrain, Oman). North Africa (Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco, Mauritania). The Levant and Iraq (Syria, Jordan, Lebanon, Iraq) and Fragile states (Yemen, Sudan, Somalia).

The central research question of this study is: What institutional factors constrain the capacity of financial markets within the MENA region to perform their essential economic functions—such as capital allocation, risk management, and liquidity provision—despite the region's substantial financial surpluses?

To address this, the study aims to accomplish four specific objectives: Examine the historical predominance of state control over financial systems in the region. Identify the disparity between formal financial sector advancements, such as increased stock exchange activity and fintech development, and actual operational effectiveness, including limited access to financing for small enterprises and a high reliance on internal funding by firms. Evaluate potential future developments under the existing institutional frameworks. Propose phased reform strategies tailored to the distinct circumstances of each of the four MENA subregions, avoiding one-size-fits-all policy solutions.

This study employs a descriptive and analytical approach, utilizing reputable secondary sources for data collection, including peer-reviewed academic literature and official reports from institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank.

The research is organized into six sections. After an introductory overview that clearly defines the primary research problem and objectives, the second section reviews relevant existing literature. The third section details the theoretical framework related to financial market development. The fourth section explores the historical evolution of financial markets in the MENA region. The fifth section assesses the future prospects and challenges facing financial markets in MENA. The study concludes with a sixth section that presents evidence-based insights and policy recommendations, tailored to the unique characteristics of each regional subgroup.

Through this comprehensive analysis, the research aims to move beyond simplistic concepts of “weak markets” and to identify the institutional and political factors that underpin challenges within the financial sector in the MENA region. This understanding is crucial for informing strategies that promote sustainable, inclusive, and diversified economic growth.

2. Literature Review

Conducting a review of existing literature is an essential methodological step that contextualizes the current study within the broader academic landscape. It facilitates the identification of existing contributions and underscores relevant methodological or analytical limitations, which this research aims to address through a more nuanced qualitative analysis.

Alotaibi et al. (2025) demonstrate that the influence of real economy sectors in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries on financial market resilience varies across different time horizons. Specifically, the insurance and transportation sectors tend to provide short-term stimulation to markets—often in response to external shocks or temporary logistics projects—while sectors such as materials, utilities, and real estate exhibit more stable, long-term effects due to their connections with infrastructure investment, inelastic demand, and economic diversification initiatives. The results from the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model indicate that the error correction rates differ significantly among sectors, reflecting varying degrees of institutional integration with the financial system. Additionally, the study highlights that reliance on hydrocarbon revenues continues to constrain certain sectors, particularly transportation, from establishing sustainable linkages with financial markets. These findings emphasize the importance of structural diversification policies in enhancing financial resilience beyond the impacts of oil price volatility.

Algaed (2021) finds that, from 1985 to 2018, the relationship between capital market development and economic growth in Saudi Arabia does not conform to theoretical expectations. While increases in the stock price index and transaction volume positively influenced per capita GDP growth, indicators of financial deepening—such as market capitalization and liquidity index—were associated with negative coefficients. This may suggest inefficiencies in channeling savings into productive investments. The ARDL cointegration test confirms the presence of a long-term relationship; however, the adjustment toward short-term disequilibria occurs gradually, at an estimated rate of approximately 24% annually. These findings imply that the linkage between financial markets and real economic activity is relatively sensitive, particularly given the country's substantial reliance on oil revenues.

Abdel-Baki (2013) demonstrates that political instability resulting from Egypt's January 25, 2011, revolution had the most significant impact on the performance of the EGX30 and EGX70 stock indices, exceeding effects from economic instability or external factors such as exchange rate fluctuations. The findings from a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) indicate a long-term cointegrating relationship between the number of participants in political protests and stock market performance, with the market response delayed by two to four days depending on the size of the listed firms. While the market experienced periods of recovery during more stable intervals, such as following the March 2011 referendum, ongoing political unrest resulted in notable downturns, particularly in the latter half of 2011. These findings underscore the sensitivity of financial markets to non-economic shocks and their limited capacity to absorb political risks.

Ayyagari et al. (2012) underscore that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), despite their significant role in job creation, face considerable financing challenges primarily due to underdeveloped legal and financial institutions. Their research indicates that bank financing remains the primary external funding source for these enterprises, while capital markets are generally underdeveloped and more suited to larger corporations. Although informal financing is common, it often correlates with slower growth and an increased risk of tax evasion. The authors attribute these issues to institutional deficiencies, such as inadequate property rights protection, limited transparency, corruption, and collateral constraints, which collectively hinder financial market performance and restrict access to finance for firms. They emphasize that strengthening institutional frameworks is crucial for enhancing the efficiency of financial markets, beyond simply expanding the size of the financial system.

Demirgüç- Kunt and Klapper (2012) note that the development of financial markets in North African countries remains relatively limited, with approximately 20% of adults possessing formal bank accounts. Small enterprises predominantly depend on internal financing, while informal saving and borrowing practices are widespread. The data suggest a shallow financial sector characterized by minimal contributions from capital markets and a strong reliance on traditional banking channels. Structural barriers to financial inclusion include low liquidity, high transaction costs, limited geographic accessibility, and an underdeveloped information infrastructure. Although innovative solutions such as mobile money have been introduced, they are currently insufficient to support a fully inclusive financial system or to facilitate the growth of high-potential firms.

Neaime (2012) demonstrates that, despite their limited institutional development, stock markets in the MENA were not immune to the shocks of the 2007–2008 global financial crisis. An analysis of financial linkages (both between MENA markets and advanced economies and among MENA markets themselves) reveals a significant increase in return and volatility spillovers during periods of crisis. This indicates that geographic diversification provides limited protection against such shocks. The heightened interconnectedness emphasizes the vulnerability of the region's financial market infrastructure and underscores the necessity for more resilient mechanisms to mitigate the impact of external shocks, which can exacerbate the effects of global crises on MENA's emerging economies.

Levine (2005) offers a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between financial system performance and economic growth. He examines the longstanding debate between perspectives that view finance as a key driver of growth, such as Schumpeter, and those that see it as a passive follower, like Robinson. Levine identifies five fundamental functions of financial systems: (1) generating information and allocating capital efficiently; (2) monitoring investments and enhancing corporate governance; (3) diversifying and managing risk; (4) mobilizing savings; and (5) facilitating trade and exchange. Empirical evidence demonstrates a strong correlation between more developed financial systems and higher GDP growth, increased capital accumulation, and improved capital allocation. Notably, this relationship appears to be causal, with

financial systems playing a critical role in alleviating firms' financing constraints. Levine underscores that the effectiveness of a financial system is determined by its capacity to perform these core functions. He further advocates for additional research into the institutional and political factors that influence the development of financial systems.

Beck and Levine (2004), in their article "Stock Markets, Banks, and Growth: Panel Evidence," conduct a comprehensive empirical analysis of the independent effects of banking sector development and stock market activity on economic growth. Using a panel dataset covering 40 countries from 1976 to 1998 and employing advanced econometric methods they find that both banking sector development and stock market activity have positive and statistically significant impacts on economic growth. These results remain consistent after controlling for potential simultaneity bias, country-specific fixed effects, and other growth-related factors.

Research Gaps: Despite the extensive body of literature on this subject, three primary gaps have been identified that this study aims to address: Firstly, there is a lack of integrated analysis combining both temporal and institutional perspectives. Most existing studies tend to focus on specific periods, such as prior to 2011 or after 2020, and do not provide a cohesive narrative encompassing historical, current, and future developments. Secondly, there is an overrepresentation of research focused on Gulf countries, while regions such as Sudan, Mauritania, Libya, and Yemen are comparatively underexplored. These countries are essential for understanding financial system transformation and exemplify mechanisms of financial resilience in environments with limited formal institutional structures. Thirdly, there is a limited critical examination of the concept of "regional financial integration." This idea is often presented as a technical solution but frequently lacks rigorous assessment of its feasibility within contexts marked by geopolitical rivalry, diverse regulatory frameworks, and weak shared institutional capabilities. In response to these gaps, this study aims to provide a comprehensive and systematic analysis that considers the institutional and political diversity across the MENA region. It will be rooted in established theories of financial development and will emphasize empirical evidence to support its findings, thereby avoiding broad or unsupported generalizations.

3. Theoretical Framework

This theoretical framework outlines the key concepts and analytical tools essential for understanding financial phenomena and the development of financial markets across different contexts. When examining the MENA region, the evolution of the financial system is closely aligned with economic theories that link financial market development to broader economic growth. Literature consistently highlights that a financial system functions not only as a channel for funding but also as a dynamic institutional environment that fosters innovation, enables efficient capital allocation, and promotes financial stability. In analyzing the transformation of the financial sector within the MENA region, this framework draws upon three principal theoretical perspectives: Schumpeter's model of financial innovation; the "finance-led growth" hypothesis as proposed

by King and Levine; and institutional analyses that associate the effectiveness of financial markets with governance quality and transparency.

3.1. Theories of Financial Development

Schumpeter's (1934) model provides a foundational theoretical framework linking financial innovation to economic growth. He argues that economic development results not solely from gradual capital accumulation but also from the implementation of "new combinations" that lead to significant structural changes within the economy. At the core of this process is the entrepreneur, who moves beyond routine management to initiate "spontaneous and discontinuous disturbances in the circular flow of economic activity," thereby challenging the existing equilibrium. To realize these new combinations (such as launching innovative products, adopting new production methods, entering new markets, or reorganizing industries) entrepreneurs require immediate access to factors of production. However, the static nature of the traditional circular flow often limits such access. This underscores the essential role of financial innovation: an effective credit system, by "creating new purchasing power," enables entrepreneurs to reallocate resources from conventional uses toward development-driven initiatives. Schumpeter emphasizes that "the banker is not primarily an intermediary in the commodity 'purchasing power,' but a producer of this commodity." Within this context, credit should be viewed not merely as a passive facilitator for transferring existing savings but as an active, innovative instrument capable of generating endogenous waves of economic development. Consequently, the financial system, particularly banking institutions, assumes the role of an institutional entrepreneur that drives the evolution of capitalism (Schumpeter, 1934: 44–54, 76–79).

Extending Schumpeter's (1934) model to the MENA region, the underperformance of financial markets can be interpreted as a failure to generate the "new combinations" necessary for sustainable growth. This is largely due to limited entrepreneurial activity and insufficient innovative credit mechanisms. In the region, credit is infrequently employed as a tool to generate new purchasing power for entrepreneurs to invest in transformative projects; instead, it is primarily directed toward routine activities or consumption. As a result, financial markets tend to serve as channels for recycling existing capital rather than acting as catalysts for growth through financial innovation, in line with Schumpeter's theoretical insights.

3.2. Finance Leads Growth

According to King and Levine (1993), the hypothesis that "finance leads growth" represents a core element of the Schumpeterian perspective on the role of the financial system in economic development. Their study, which analyzed data from 80 countries between 1960 and 1989, suggests that measures of financial development (such as financial depth, the relative importance of commercial banks compared to the central bank, and the proportion of credit allocated to the private sector) are reliable predictors of future economic growth over periods ranging from 10 to 30 years. The authors argue that this relationship extends beyond simple correlation; rather, financial systems actively influence long-term growth by facilitating physical capital accumulation

and enhancing the efficiency of capital allocation. Their primary conclusion emphasizes that "finance does not merely follow growth it drives it" (King & Levine, 1993: 717-719, 730, 735).

Extending King and Levine's (1993) "finance leads growth" framework to the MENA region suggests that underdeveloped financial markets may be associated with delays in essential financial functions (such as mobilizing savings, screening investment opportunities, monitoring firms, and managing risk) even when financial resources are present. Key indicators, including financial depth, the efficiency of private-sector credit allocation, and the operational independence of commercial banks from the central bank, are generally relatively low across much of the region. This could limit the financial system's capacity to support innovation and improve capital efficiency. Additionally, as indicated by King and Levine's research, early levels of financial development tend to be predictive of economic growth over the subsequent 10 to 30 years. Consequently, institutional weaknesses within the financial systems of the MENA region, particularly outside the Gulf countries, may be fundamental factors contributing to slower sustainable growth, rather than solely a consequence of it.

3.3. Institutional Analysis

In evaluating the effectiveness of financial markets, institutional analysis plays a vital role in understanding differences in financial development and economic performance across nations. According to Acemoglu and Johnson (2005), "property rights institutions"—which protect individuals from expropriation by the state or political elites—are crucial for establishing an environment conducive to investment and sustained financial growth. These institutions, characterized by effective limitations on executive power and independent legal protections for private property, help mitigate risks such as nationalization or arbitrary confiscation. Consequently, they enhance investor confidence and encourage consistent capital inflows into financial markets. Conversely, the authors note that "contracting institutions," responsible for regulating private contractual relationships, have a limited impact on overall economic growth and financial development, although they do influence the structure of financial intermediation (e.g., bank-based versus market-based systems). Therefore, strong institutional governance is essential for creating a resilient and efficient financial system: without sufficient constraints on state-led expropriation, financial markets tend to be fragile and inefficient in resource allocation (Acemoglu & Johnson, 2005: 949-953, 984).

Extending this framework to the financial markets in the MENA region reveals that a primary challenge is the weakness of property rights institutions—specifically, the absence of effective mechanisms to restrain state and elite expropriation. In environments with significant government influence and politically motivated interventions, investors lack the fundamental protections needed to manage risk and make long-term commitments to financial markets.

3.4. Financial Market Assessment Indicators

According to the Global Financial Stability Report (IMF, 2024), a comprehensive set of sector-specific indicators is used to evaluate various

aspects of the financial system. The report emphasizes that assessments of financial stability rely on key metrics such as yield spreads between investment-grade and high-yield corporate bonds; banking stress indicators, including non-performing loan ratios and the Common Equity Tier 1 (CET1) capital ratio; capital flow trends into emerging markets; and liquidity measures for bond funds, such as repo activity and exposure to illiquid assets. The report further underscores the importance of debt-related indicators, including the corporate debt-to-GDP ratio adjusted for maturity profiles and the interest coverage ratio, as essential tools for identifying potential corporate vulnerabilities. It also highlights stress indicators within the commercial real estate sector, such as total outstanding debt and financing gaps, which may serve as early warning signals. Additionally, the IMF emphasizes the importance of institutional behavior indicators, such as investor redemptions from funds and leverage levels in private credit markets, as proxies for systemic risks beyond the traditional banking sector (IMF, 2024b: 17, 27, 33–38).

4. Historical Evolution of Financial Markets in the MENA Region

Financial markets within the MENA region have undergone significant development; however, the pace and scope of progress vary considerably among individual countries. Over time, different components of the financial system have evolved at differing rates. Notably, banking infrastructure has experienced substantial growth in certain countries, particularly within the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), while capital markets, including equity, bond, foreign exchange, and derivatives markets, remain underdeveloped or fragile outside of these nations. These disparities are shaped by longstanding geopolitical, economic, and institutional factors that continue to influence the region's financial landscape.

The development of financial markets in the MENA region over the last two decades of the twentieth century exhibited significant variation among individual countries. In most parts of the region, the financial system remained primarily bank-centric, with capital markets, including equity and bond markets, being underdeveloped, illiquid, and lacking strong institutional governance. Between 1993 and 2002, several countries (particularly within the Gulf Cooperation Council as well as Egypt) implemented comprehensive financial reforms. These initiatives encompassed the privatization of financial institutions, restructuring of banking sectors, enhancements to market infrastructure, and the adoption of improved transparency and regulatory oversight. These efforts resulted in notable progress, such as increased numbers of listed companies and heightened trading activity, especially during the second half of the 1990s. Furthermore, countries established electronic trading platforms, enacted new investor protection legislation, and formed independent regulatory agencies. Nevertheless, progress across the region remained uneven. While nations such as Egypt, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE developed relatively more advanced financial markets, others, including Yemen, Syria, and Sudan, continued to lack active capital markets and remained predominantly reliant on traditional bank-based financing. Overall, despite these advancements, the financial markets in the region, as of around 2000–2001, had not yet attained the depth or efficiency observed in Asian or Latin American markets. They continued to face challenges associated with "financial repression," such as administered

interest rates, restrictions on capital flows, and predominantly state-directed credit allocation, all of which impeded the efficient distribution of financial resources (IMF, 2003: 2–4, 15–17).

The first two decades of the twenty-first century have been characterized by significant and uneven changes in the financial markets across the MENA region. External shocks—including the global financial crisis, energy price fluctuations, and the economic impacts of the pandemic—have coincided with internal challenges such as political unrest, armed conflicts, and institutional fragmentation. This convergence of factors has resulted in diverse developmental pathways throughout the region. While Gulf Cooperation Council countries have made substantial progress in developing and strengthening their financial markets, many nations in North Africa and the Levant continue to face core issues related to political instability and financial instability. Nevertheless, advancements, particularly within the most developed markets, remain susceptible to volatility, as they are often dependent on government support or external conditions rather than on the development of resilient and sustainable financial institutions.

An analysis of financial market development in the MENA region reveals a notable gap between financial depth and financial inclusion. Although the region ranks second globally in terms of financial depth—measured by private credit-to-GDP ratios—following East Asia and OECD countries, this financial depth does not necessarily reflect widespread access for individuals and small enterprises. At the time, only 21.3% of adults held bank accounts used for borrowing purposes, and deposit account ownership varied significantly across countries—from 10.4% in Yemen and 19.2% in Syria to over one deposit account per adult in Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Lebanon, and Iran. This disparity can be partly attributed to the concentrated structure of the financial system, wherein banks held 63.6% of total financial assets in 2008 and primarily directed credit toward governments and large corporations. Such a focus has limited access to formal financing for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Consequently, many SMEs relied on alternative financing sources, such as trade credit; for example, approximately half of small firms in Yemen reported obtaining credit from suppliers. Moreover, the availability of microfinance services varies considerably across the region. While around 70% of microfinance institutions were concentrated in Morocco, the sector was largely absent in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, with the exceptions of Bahrain and Saudi Arabia. Regulatory barriers also played a role in limiting financial inclusion. Strict Know-Your-Customer (KYC) requirements, restrictions on the use of agent-based delivery channels, and the lack of modern laws supporting secured transactions for movable assets hindered access to financial services. As a result, many MENA countries tended to score low on the World Bank’s “Legal Rights” indicator within the Ease of Doing Business report (Pearce, 2011: 5–6, 10, 13, 19, 22–23).

4.1. The Global Financial Crisis (2008–2009)

During the 2008–2009 global financial crisis, financial markets in the MENA region were not directly affected by the deteriorating assets responsible for bank failures in the United States and Europe. Instead, the region experienced

the crisis's impacts through complex and indirect channels. The primary shocks stemmed from a significant reduction in oil revenues, decreased global demand affecting exports, tourism, and remittance inflows, as well as a sudden tightening of international financing conditions and a decline in investor risk appetite. These developments led to notable declines in equity markets across Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries; for instance, Dubai's stock index fell approximately 73% from January 2008 to March 2009. Although real estate prices had begun declining in the summer of 2008, the downward trend accelerated sharply after September 2008 amid escalating global financial instability. Additionally, credit risk indicators increased substantially; Dubai's credit default swap (CDS) spreads reached approximately 1,000 basis points, reflecting heightened market concerns regarding the ability of financial institutions to rollover short-term debt. In response, regional authorities quickly implemented measures to stabilize the financial sector. These included liquidity injections by central banks, expansion of deposit insurance schemes, and mobilization of sovereign wealth funds, particularly in Kuwait and Qatar, to recapitalize banks through equity investments or by repatriating foreign assets into domestic banking systems. Despite the scale and promptness of these interventions, they were insufficient to fully restore the functioning of credit markets. Credit channels remained constrained, and many profitable enterprises continued to face difficulties securing adequate financing. In oil-importing countries such as Egypt, Morocco, and Lebanon, initial market impacts appeared limited. However, these countries subsequently experienced secondary effects, including declines in export revenues, increased financial pressure on banking systems, and rising risks of non-performing loans. While they avoided immediate financial collapse, their underlying vulnerabilities (stemming from limited integration into global markets and heavy dependence on external inflows such as remittances and foreign direct investment) made them susceptible to gradual economic deterioration as the global recession deepened (IMF, 2009: 1, 6-7, 11-14). Ultimately, the financial crisis in the MENA region was characterized not only by liquidity and solvency challenges but also by a significant erosion of confidence in the capacity of financial markets to effectively absorb external shocks. The absence of self-correcting market mechanisms meant that governments played a central role in maintaining stability—acting actively through interventions, rather than relying solely on natural market adjustments.

4.2. The Arab Spring (2011)

The impact of the Arab Spring on financial markets within the MENA region warrants a contextual analysis, taking into account subregional differences. Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries generally mitigated initial disruptions by leveraging their substantial oil surpluses, approaching USD 400 billion in 2011, as fiscal buffers to sustain external stability. In contrast, other areas of the region experienced varying degrees of economic shocks that persisted over time. In North Africa, unrest in Tunisia and Egypt led to significant declines in tourism revenue and remittance flows, particularly as returning migrants from Libya increased labor market pressures. These developments contributed to decreases in foreign exchange reserves and widened external deficits. Similarly, in the Levant region (Jordan and Lebanon), financial markets faced challenges not only from domestic vulnerabilities but also from spillover effects of the Syrian crisis, including disrupted supply chains, declining exports,

and rising energy import costs. In fragile states such as Yemen and Syria, political instability resulted in the near-total breakdown of core financial market functions, leading to diminished confidence in banking institutions, reduced borrowing capacity for the state, and a sharp increase in non-performing loans. Despite the different experiences across countries, a common and concerning trend emerged: increasing reliance on domestic borrowing to finance current account deficits. This dependence increasingly constrained private sector access to credit and weakened the financial system's ability to channel savings into productive investments. Overall, the Arab Spring's repercussions extended beyond short-term market volatility, revealing underlying institutional vulnerabilities. While the severity of these weaknesses varied across North Africa, the Levant, and fragile states, a shared critical deficiency was evident: the absence of endogenous market mechanisms capable of absorbing systemic shocks (IMF, 2012: 1–6).

4.3. Financial Market Developments in MENA

Over the past two decades, the MENA region has experienced varying levels of progress in financial market development. In Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, capital markets have shown significant growth, as evidenced by increased stock market capitalization and heightened activity in initial public offerings (IPOs). These economies have also experienced periodic yet meaningful growth in sukuk issuance. Additionally, GCC nations have advanced their fintech sectors by establishing regulatory sandboxes, licensing digital banks—particularly in Saudi Arabia and the UAE—launching specialized fintech hubs, and exploring central bank digital currencies (CBDCs). Nonetheless, secondary market trading remains limited, primarily due to low equity liquidity and wide bid-ask spreads. These factors restrict active trading, especially in shares of non-state-owned enterprises. In non-GCC MENA countries, financial markets tend to be heavily reliant on the banking sector, with significant government involvement through direct ownership and preferential credit allocation to the public sector. This dependence is reflected in underdeveloped bond and equity markets and a limited presence of institutional investors. While microfinance institutions are operative in countries such as Egypt and Morocco, and digital financial services—particularly mobile banking—have expanded in Jordan and Egypt, these developments have yet to yield substantial financial deepening. Challenges such as weak infrastructure and underdeveloped local-currency government bond markets continue to impede progress. Low-income and conflict-affected nations within MENA face additional obstacles, including institutional fragility, monetary instability, and insufficient legal frameworks, all of which hinder the growth of the financial sector. Despite the potential for microfinance to alleviate poverty and reduce inequality, access to financial services remains limited. Overall, financial markets across much of the region remain less developed compared to other emerging economies, particularly in terms of bond and equity market depth and efficiency. Factors contributing to this include infrequent sovereign bond issuance, minimal secondary market activity, and restrictions on participation by non-resident investors. The report emphasizes that comprehensive reform efforts are vital for advancing financial development. Key priorities include reducing state dominance in banking, promoting increased competition through new market entrants, establishing active local-currency government bond markets to serve as benchmarks for

private-sector debt, expanding the role of institutional investors, and relaxing capital account restrictions to support greater regional financial integration (IMF, 2024a: 36–45).

4.3.1. FinTech Development in the MENA Region

The MENA region is experiencing a notable growth in the adoption of financial technology (FinTech). Investment levels in FinTech companies have increased significantly, rising from USD 44 million in 2018–2019 to USD 160 million in 2020, then expanding to USD 587 million in 2021, and reaching USD 925 million in 2022, despite a global slowdown in FinTech investments during the same period. A considerable share of this investment is concentrated in a few key countries: the United Arab Emirates (37%), Saudi Arabia (26%), and Egypt (23%), highlighting their roles as regional FinTech hubs. The United Arab Emirates leads with 465 FinTech firms, accounting for 47% of the region's total, followed by Bahrain with 120 companies, Egypt with 112, and Saudi Arabia with 82. This growth is primarily driven by the availability of advanced digital infrastructure, supportive government initiatives, and relatively clear regulatory frameworks—particularly in Gulf countries—which collectively foster an environment conducive to innovation and bolster confidence among both investors and consumers (Ameziane & Djabat, 2023: 7–10).

5. The Future and Challenges of Financial Markets in MENA

Given the region's enduring structural challenges—including slow economic growth, institutional vulnerabilities, and increasing public debt—the outlook for financial markets in the MENA, encompassing banking, non-bank financial institutions, capital markets, payment systems, and alternative finance, depends on more than just expanding financial services or modernizing regulatory frameworks. It fundamentally requires redefining the relationship between the state and the economy through the development of a "learning state" approach. In the Gulf countries, which benefit from substantial revenues due to elevated energy prices, the future of financial markets will depend on their ability to convert temporary surpluses into productive, transparently managed investments that mitigate the risk of resource dependence and prevent the resource curse. For oil-importing nations such as Egypt, Jordan, and Tunisia, financial market development remains fragile without necessary reforms addressing governance deficiencies, data transparency issues, and unsustainable public debt levels. Institutionalizing evidence-based fiscal policies, disciplined expenditure management, and performance-oriented accountability are essential to ensure that financial deepening translates into meaningful growth rather than superficial improvements. In fragile contexts like Iraq, Yemen, and Libya, financial markets often focus on survival rather than development, lacking the foundational institutional infrastructure needed for stability and investor confidence. Global experience shows that recovery begins with building trust—trust founded on transparent public spending, effective accountability mechanisms, and access to reliable data. Ultimately, the future of MENA's financial markets will be determined less by liquidity or the number of financial institutions and more by governance quality—specifically, the capacity of the state to measure, strategize, experiment, and adapt. This involves learning from past experiences, implementing policies based on evidence rather than vested

interests, and engaging citizens and investors as active partners in governance and accountability. Without a fundamental shift from a resource-dependent model to one focused on institutional learning and development, the financial markets in MENA will remain vulnerable to external shocks and lack the capacity to support diversified, inclusive economic growth that provides meaningful employment opportunities for youth and women (World Bank, 2022: x, xxiii–xxiv, 37).

5.1. Challenges in MENA Financial Markets

Financial markets in the MENA are comparatively less developed than those in other emerging regions, particularly within their non-banking sectors, such as equity and corporate bond markets. Data based on stock market capitalization and corporate bond issuance relative to GDP consistently position MENA at lower tiers among developing regions. In 2017, the region's stock market capitalization stood at only 42% of GDP, significantly below East Asia's 179%. This gap is even more evident in the non-EU Southern Mediterranean countries, where the ratio drops to approximately 27%. As of 2015, corporate bond issuance in the region remained limited, with notable disparities across countries: Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) nations displayed relatively more advanced markets, whereas issuance was minimal or non-existent in non-GCC oil-exporting and oil-importing countries. A primary factor underlying this underperformance is the predominance of the banking sector, which often limits the development of non-bank financial services. Rather than improving financing efficiency, this sector dominance tends to create systemic biases in credit allocation, favoring state-owned enterprises and politically connected firms, primarily through public banks. Consequently, the financial system encounters challenges in effectively serving small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), due to both supply-side constraints and demand-side factors. This environment hampers the development of a competitive banking sector capable of channeling resources toward the most productive investments (Arezki & Senbet, 2020: 3, 6–8).

Financial markets across the Middle East and North Africa, including GCC countries, the Levant, North Africa, and fragile economies, are currently facing significant structural challenges that extend beyond mere stock market fluctuations. These issues are affecting their fundamental ability to mobilize financing and maintain financial stability. Since early 2022, amid an unprecedented tightening of global financial conditions, middle-income and emerging economies in the region, particularly those with weaker macroeconomic fundamentals, have experienced more pronounced contractions in financing conditions compared to other emerging markets worldwide. This trend is evidenced by a substantial increase in yields on foreign-currency-denominated sovereign bonds in countries such as Egypt and Tunisia, reflecting declining investor confidence and raising concerns regarding external dependencies and fiscal sustainability. As investor confidence diminishes and borrowing costs rise, issuance of Eurobonds from the region has decreased significantly totaling USD 3.65 billion in the first nine months of 2022, compared to over USD 30 billion during the same period in the previous year. This decline has resulted in an estimated external financing gap of approximately USD 24.5 billion to cover maturing bonds. In the absence of effective external financing

options, many countries have increasingly relied on domestic banks to fund fiscal deficits. This shift has strengthened the interdependence between sovereign debt and the banking sector, thereby increasing the risk of financial contagion. Additionally, the region has experienced an outbound flow of USD 3.8 billion in foreign portfolio capital since mid-2021, with more than half of these outflows occurring after February 2022. This underscores the vulnerability of these markets to external shocks and highlights the limited development of alternative financing instruments. As a result, even in their primary functions—such as sovereign debt issuance and secondary market trading—financial markets in the MENA region often function as vulnerabilities rather than stable mechanisms for resource mobilization and risk management, posing challenges to overall economic stability (IMF, 2022: 5–6, 9).

6. Findings and Recommendations

The financial landscape across the MENA region is highly diverse, comprising four distinct subregions, each characterized by unique market dynamics, challenges, and opportunities. Approaches that treat the region as a homogeneous entity or rely on oversimplified classifications such as "advanced" versus "underdeveloped" are insufficient and may lead to misinterpretations. It is crucial to acknowledge the complex environment in which formal financial institutions—such as legal frameworks, stock exchanges, and regulatory authorities—operate alongside ongoing deficiencies in fundamental market functions, including risk assessment, savings mobilization, and capital allocation.

In the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, significant progress has been made in developing sophisticated financial infrastructure, featuring advanced stock exchanges, substantial sovereign wealth funds, digital payment platforms, and Sharia-compliant financing options. However, much of this infrastructure often functions more as an instrument for government policy implementation rather than as a genuine market mechanism. Elevated liquidity levels are frequently driven by direct state support rather than investor confidence or market efficiency. The presence of listed companies predominantly reflects symbolic progress rather than meaningful economic diversification. As a result, financial systems tend to prioritize policy objectives over rigorous evaluations of enterprise performance, underscoring the need to reinforce institutional integrity.

In North Africa and the Levant, systemic vulnerabilities are common. Countries such as Egypt, Tunisia, Jordan, and Lebanon experience persistent issues—including liquidity shortages, underdeveloped bond markets, withdrawal of institutional investors, and gaps in transparency and governance. While legal frameworks are generally established on paper, political will and institutional capacity to enforce regulations are often lacking. The absence of effective independent regulatory bodies and investor protections undermines market credibility, which can lead to speculative activity or influence from political connections.

In fragile states—namely Yemen, Syria, Sudan, and Libya—the traditional financial sector has largely disintegrated. Economic activity predominantly relies on survival strategies such as remittances, basic commodity trading, informal cash economies, and parallel currency systems.

Standard financial institutions, including stock exchanges and central banks, are either non-operational or ineffective, and unified payment systems are absent.

Given this fragmented environment, uniform solutions are unlikely to be effective. Instead, strategies should be tailored to the specific needs of each subregion: For fragile states, priority should be given to safeguarding critical financial flows—such as remittances—and establishing foundational institutional structures, including reliable payment systems, operational central banks, and a basic legal framework to protect market participants. In North Africa and the Levant, efforts should focus on developing government and private bond markets to diversify funding sources, establish credible yield curves, and attract institutional investors. Within the GCC, emphasis should be placed on enhancing financial governance by establishing truly independent regulatory authorities that are insulated from political influence, thereby transforming markets into genuine economic institutions rather than mere policy instruments.

The overarching objective is not merely to improve existing markets but to reconstruct financial systems in which trust is restored among investors, capital is allocated efficiently, and the financial sector effectively supports economic growth. Achieving this requires a fundamental shift in the relationship between the state and the market—from models where the state owns and directly funds markets to models where it acts as a regulator and facilitator, nurturing resilient institutions.

Additional considerations include establishing an independent regional financial authority to support the development of harmonized standards without imposing artificial integration. It is also advisable to leverage financial technology (fintech) innovations to address regulatory and administrative challenges. Furthermore, efforts should be made to increase retail investor participation through improved financial literacy and strengthened legal protections. Finally, the role of the state should be reaffirmed as a facilitator and regulator, rather than a direct participant in the market.

7. Conclusion

The MENA region does not currently face a shortage of capital; rather, it suffers from a persistent lack of institutions capable of effectively channeling capital toward meaningful economic objectives. Although progress has been made through the development of modern stock exchanges, notable listings, and expanding financial infrastructure, these advancements have yet to translate into efficient markets that substantially support broader economic development. Much of this progress remains primarily aligned with state objectives rather than market principles—in many cases serving political agendas or official development plans instead of fostering allocative efficiency or safeguarding investor rights.

The core challenge lies not in the volume of liquidity or the variety of financial instruments, but in the absence of an independent, transparent institutional framework that governs the relationships among the state, the market, issuers, and investors. The goal should not be to adopt an excessively liberal model or diminish the role of the state; rather, it is important to

recalibrate the state's function—shifting from a direct market participant to a neutral steward of market integrity and regulation.

Building stable and resilient financial systems requires more than temporary measures or interventions. It necessitates the development of endogenous risk assessment mechanisms, institutions capable of enforcing transparency, and credible safeguards for all market participants, regardless of political or social background.

In an increasingly transparent and well-governed global environment, markets lacking credibility struggle to attract sustained investment or generate significant employment opportunities for youth. Such progress will remain elusive unless the perception of the financial system shifts from being a tool for political implementation to a domain focused on value creation.

Without a fundamental shift in the state's role—from “owner and financier” to “regulator and guarantor”—financial markets in the region are likely to remain superficial and ineffective at mobilizing savings, allocating capital efficiently, and managing risks appropriately.

Ultimately, the challenge extends beyond increasing listings or expanding market size; it involves developing a financial system rooted in trust, governed by integrity, and aligned with broader economic objectives rather than political interests. Only through this approach can sustainable, inclusive growth be realized growth that reflects the region's complexities and aspirations, from the Gulf to the Atlantic.

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